

Derivative Valuation Framework

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ABSTRACT

Derivatives valuation bears counterparty credit risk and requires credit valuation adjustment (CVA). This article presents a framework for pricing derivatives by taking counterparty credit risk into account. Our framework shows how to perform the risky valuation and how to calculate the bilateral CVA at a portfolio level. This framework can easily incorporate various credit mitigation techniques, such as netting agreements and margin agreements, and can capture wrong way risk. Numerical results show that these credit mitigation techniques and wrong/right way risk have significant impacts on CVA.

Key Words: credit value adjustment (CVA), credit risk modeling, financial derivative valuation, collateralization, margin and netting.

In the market, risk-free values are quoted for most financial derivatives. In other words, credit risk is not captured. Historical experience shows that credit risk often leads to significant losses. Therefore, it is obvious to all market participants that credit risk should be taken into account when reporting the fair value of any defaultable derivative. The adjustment to the risk-free value is known as the credit value adjustment (CVA). CVA offers an opportunity for banks to dynamically price credit risk into new trades and has become a common practice in the financial industry, especially for trading books. By definition, CVA is the difference between the risk-free value and the true (or risky or defaultable) value that takes into account the possibility of default. The risk-free value is what brokers quote or what trading systems or models normally report. The risky value, however, is a relatively less explored and less transparent area, which is the main challenge and core theme for credit risk measurement and management (see Xiao (2015) and Xiao (2017)).

Three different recovery models exist in the literature. The default payoff is either 1) a fraction of par (Madan and Unal (1998)), 2) a fraction of an equivalent default-free bond (Jarrow and Turnbull (1995)), or 3) a fraction of market value (Duffie and Singleton (1999)). The last one is most commonly used in the market. In their paper, Duffie and Singleton (1999) do not clearly state whether the market value of a defaultable derivative is a risky value or a risk-free value. Instead, the authors implicitly treat the market value as a risky value because the market price therein evolves in a defaultable manner. Otherwise, they cannot obtain the desired result. However, most of the later papers in the literature mistakenly think that the market value of a defaultable derivative is a risk-free value. Consequently, the results are incorrect. For instance, the current most popular CVA model described by Pykhtin and Zhu (2007), and Gregory (2009) is inappropriate in theory because the authors do not distinguish risky value and risk-free value when they conduct a risky valuation (i.e. valuing a defaultable derivative). In fact, the model has never been rigorously proved.

There is an intuitive way of understanding these backward induction behaviours: We can think that any defaultable derivative with bilateral credit risk embeds two default options. In other words, when entering a defaultable financial transaction, one party grants the other party an option to default and, at the

same time, also receives an option to default itself. In theory, default may occur at any time. Therefore, default options are American style options that normally require a backward induction valuation.

We explicitly indicate that, within the context of risky valuation, the market value of a defaultable derivative is actually a risky value rather than a risk-free value, because a firm may default at any future time even if it survives today. An intuitive explanation is that after charging the upfront CVA, one already converted the market value of a defaultable derivative from the risk-free value to the risky value.

The rest of this paper is organized as follows: Basic setup is provided in Section 1; pricing unilateral defaultable derivatives and their unilateral CVAs is discussed in Section 2; valuing bilateral asymmetric defaultable derivatives and their bilateral CVAs is elaborated on in Section 3; a practical framework that embraces netting agreements, margining agreements, and wrong/right way risk is proposed in Section 4, and the numerical results are presented in Section 5. The conclusions are given in Section 6.

1. Basic Setup

The default model is based on the reduced-form approach proposed by Duffie and Singleton (1999) and Jarrow and Turnbull (1994), which does not explain the event of default endogenously, but characterizes it exogenously by a jump process. The stopping (or default) time τ is modeled as a Cox arrival process (also known as a doubly stochastic Poisson process) whose first jump occurs at default with a stochastic hazard rate or arrival intensity $h(t)$.

It is well-known that the survival probability, conditional on a realization path, from time t to s in this framework is defined by

$$S(t, s) := \Pr(\tau > s \mid \tau > t, Z) = \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (1a)$$

where Z is the firm-specific state process that helps forecast that firm's default. The default probability, conditional on the realization path, for the period (t, s) in this framework is defined by

$$Q(t, s) = \Pr(\tau \leq s \mid \tau > t, Z) = 1 - S(t, s) = 1 - \exp\left(-\int_t^s h(u) du\right) \quad (1b)$$

Applying the law of iterated expectations, we express the expected survival probability for the period (t, s) as

$$\bar{S}(t, s) = E \left[\exp \left(- \int_t^s h(u) du \right) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (2a)$$

where $E \{ \bullet | \mathcal{F}_t \}$ is the expectation conditional on the \mathcal{F}_t . The expected default probability for the period (t, s) is expressed as

$$\bar{Q}(t, s) = 1 - \bar{S}(t, s) = 1 - E \left[\exp \left(- \int_t^s h(u) du \right) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (2b)$$

The binomial default rule considers only two possible states: default or survival. For a discrete one-period (t, s) economy, at the end of the period a defaultable derivative either defaults with the default probability $Q(t, s)$ or survives with the survival probability $S(t, s)$. Assume that the market value of the defaultable derivative at time s is $V^D(s)$. The default payoff is a fraction of the market value given by $\varphi(s)V^D(s)$, where $\varphi(s)$ is the default recovery rate at time s , whereas the survival payoff is equal to the market value $V^D(s)$ itself. Therefore, the risky value of the derivative, conditional on the realization path, is the discounted expectation of the payoffs, given by

$$V^D(t) = D(t, s) \left(Q(t, s) \varphi(s) V^D(s) + S(t, s) V^D(s) \right) \quad (3a)$$

where

$$D(t, s) = \exp \left[- \int_t^s r(u) du \right] \quad (3b)$$

where $D(t, s)$ denotes the stochastic risk-free discount factor at t for the maturity s and $r(u)$ denotes the risk-free short rate at time u ($t \leq u \leq s$).

If the derivative survives at time s , the survival value is equal to the market value. However, the derivative may default at any time after s . Therefore, the present survival value or the market value at time s is a risky value. In other words, for risk-free valuations, the market value is a risk-free value, but for risky

valuations, the market value is actually a risky value. An intuitive explanation is that one already converted the market value from the risk-free value to the risky value after charging the upfront CVA.

2. Unilateral Defaultable Derivatives Valuation and Unilateral CVA

Two parties are denoted as A and B . The unilateral credit risk assumes that only one party is defaultable and the other one is default-free. In this section, we assume that party A is default-free, whereas party B is defaultable. All calculations are from the perspective of party A . Let the valuation date be t . We study single payment cases first.

2.1. Single Payment Cases

Consider a defaultable derivative that promises to pay a X_T from party B to party A at maturity date T , and nothing before date T . The payoff X_T may be positive or negative, i.e. the derivative may be either an asset or a liability to each party. The risk-free value of the derivative at valuation date t is given by

$$V^F(t) = E\{D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (4)$$

where $D(t, T)$ is the risk-free discount factor defined in (3b).

We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period.

Proposition 1: *The unilateral risky value of the single payment derivative is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{C_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (5a)$$

where

$$C_B(t, T) = \exp\left[-\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} c_B(t + i\Delta t)\Delta t\right] \quad (5b)$$

$$c_B(t + i\Delta t) = r(t + i\Delta t) + 1_{V^D(t+(i+1)\Delta t) \geq 0} h_B(t + i\Delta t)(1 - \varphi_B(t + i\Delta t)) \quad (5c)$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise.

Proof: See the Appendix.

Compared to the risk-free valuation (4), the risky valuation (5) is substantially complex. The intermediate values are vital to determine the final price. For a small time interval, the current risky value has a dependence on the future risky value. Only on the final payment date T , the value of the derivative and the maximum amount of information needed to determine the risk-adjusted discount factor are revealed. This type of problem can be best solved by working backwards in time, with the later risky value feeding into the earlier ones, so that the process builds on itself in a recursive fashion, which is referred to as backward induction. The most popular backward induction valuation algorithms are lattice/tree and regression-based Monte Carlo.

In theory, a default may happen at any time. The Continuous-Time Risky Valuation Model, or simply the Continuous-Time Model (CTM), assumes that a defaultable derivative is continuously defaultable. Proposition 1 can be further expressed in the form of the CTM as:

Corollary 1.1: *The unilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{\bar{C}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (6a)$$

where

$$\bar{C}_B(t, T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T \bar{c}_B(u)du\right] \quad (6b)$$

$$\bar{c}_B(u) = r(u) + 1_{V^D(u) \geq 0} h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (6c)$$

The proof of this corollary becomes straightforward, according to Proposition 1, by taking the limit as Δt approaches zero.

Proposition 1 provides a general form for pricing a unilateral defaultable single payment derivative. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that the payoff X_T is non-negative, we derive the following corollary:

Corollary 1.2: *If the payoff X_T is non-negative, the risky value of the single payment derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{\widehat{C}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (7a)$$

where

$$\widehat{C}_B(t, T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T \widehat{c}_B(u)du\right] \quad (7b)$$

$$\widehat{c}_B(u) = r(u) + h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (7c)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to (6) by setting $V^D(u) \geq 0$. Since the payoff X_T is non-negative, the intermediate value $V^D(u)$ is also non-negative.

The risky valuation becomes quite simple when the payoff is non-negative. This corollary says that a single non-negative payment defaultable derivative can be priced using the present value of the promised payoff X_T discounted by the risk-adjusted discount rate $\widehat{c}_B(u)$ instead of the risk-free rate $r(u)$.

By definition, the corresponding CVA of the single non-negative payment derivative can be expressed as

$$CVA^U(t) = V^F(t) - V^D(t) = E\{D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} - E\{\widehat{C}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (8)$$

Since $\widehat{C}_B(t, T)$ is always smaller than $D(t, T)$, the CVA is, in this case, a credit charge. The credit charge covering party A's potential loss comes from the scenario of party B's default when party A is in the money in the portfolio.

Under the CTM, a unilateral defaultable derivative has an embedded American style default option, which is continuously defaultable. Since American options are difficult to hedge, a common practice in the market is to use Bermudan options to approximate American ones. Consequently, we assume that a default may only happen at some discrete times. A natural selection is to assume that a default may occur only on the payment dates. The Discrete-Time Risky Valuation Model, or simply the Discrete-Time Model (DTM), assumes that a defaultable derivative may only default on payment dates.

Proposition 2: *The unilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E[G_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (9a)$$

where

$$G_B(t, T) = D(t, T)[1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0} Q_B(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T))] \quad (9b)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

Here we may consider $G_B(t, T)$ as the risk-adjusted discount factor. Proposition 2 states that the unilateral risky valuation of the single payoff derivative has a dependence on the sign of the payoff. If the payoff is positive, the risky value is equal to the risk-free value minus the discounted potential loss. Otherwise, the risky value is equal to the risk-free value.

The corresponding unilateral CVA of the single payment derivative under the DTM can be expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} CVA^U(t) &= V^F(t) - V^D(t) = E\{D(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} - E\{G_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \\ &= E[1_{X_T \geq 0} D(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T))Q_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \end{aligned} \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) shows that if the payoff is in the money, the CVA is a credit charge equal to the discounted potential loss. If the payoff is out of the money, the CVA is zero.

Proposition 2 has a general form that applies in a particular situation in which we assume that the payoff X_T is non-negative.

Corollary 2.1: *If the payoff X_T is non-negative, the risky value of the single payment derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E[\bar{G}_B(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t] \quad (11a)$$

where

$$\bar{G}_B(t, T) = D(t, T)[1 - Q_B(t, T)(1 - \varphi_B(T))] = D(t, T)(S_B(t, T) + \varphi_B(T)Q_B(t, T)) \quad (11b)$$

The proof of this corollary is straightforward according to Proposition 2 by setting $X_T \geq 0$. Equations (11) are consistent with equations (3).

2.2. Multiple Payments Cases

Suppose that a defaultable derivative has m cash flows. Any of these cash flows may be positive or negative. Let the m cash flows be represented as X_1, \dots, X_m with payment dates T_1, \dots, T_m . The risk-free price of the derivative is given by

$$V^F(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\{D(t, T_i) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (12)$$

We divide any payment date period (T_{i-1}, T_i) into n_i very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period.

Proposition 3: *The unilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[(C_B(t, T_i) X_i) | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (13a)$$

where

$$C_B(t, T_i) = \exp\left[- \sum_{j=0}^{\sum_{k=1}^i n_k - 1} c_B(t + j\Delta t) \Delta t \right] \quad (13b)$$

$$c_B(t + j\Delta t) = r(t + j\Delta t) + 1_{V^D(t+(j+1)\Delta t) \geq 0} h_B(t + j\Delta t) (1 - \varphi_B(t + j\Delta t)) \quad (13c)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

If we model default in a continuous-time setting, the Proposition 3 can be further expressed as follows.

Corollary 3.1: *The unilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[(\bar{C}_B(t, T_i) X_i) | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (14)$$

where

$$\bar{C}_B(t, T_i) = \exp\left[- \int_t^{T_i} \bar{c}_B(u) du \right] \quad (14b)$$

$$\bar{c}_B(u) = r(u) + 1_{V^D(u) \geq 0} h_B(u) (1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (14c)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained, according to Proposition 3, by taking the limit as Δt approaches zero.

Proposition 3 has a general form that applies in a particular situation in which we assume that all the payoffs are non-negative.

Corollary 3.2: *If all the payoffs are non-negative, the risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\widehat{C}_B(t, T_i) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (15a)$$

where

$$\widehat{C}_B(t, T_i) = \exp\left[-\int_t^{T_i} \widehat{c}_B(u) du\right] \quad (15b)$$

$$\widehat{c}_B(u) = r(u) + h_B(u)(1 - \varphi_B(u)) \quad (15c)$$

The proof of this corollary is straightforward, according to (14), by setting $V^D(u) \geq 0$.

If we assume that a default may occur only on the payment dates, the result is the following proposition in a discrete-time setting.

Proposition 4: *The unilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} G_B(T_j, T_{j+1})\right) X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (16a)$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$G_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left[1 - 1_{(X_{j+1} + V^D(T_{j+1})) \geq 0} Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}))\right] \quad (16b)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

Similar to Proposition 3, the individual payoffs under Proposition 4 cannot be evaluated separately. The current risky value depends on the future risky value. This type of problem is usually solved using backward induction algorithms.

Proposition 4 has a general form that applies in a particular situation where we assume that all payoffs are non-negative.

Corollary 4.1: *If all the payoffs are non-negative, the risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} \bar{G}_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_i \right] \quad (17a)$$

Where $t = T_0$ and

$$\bar{G}_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) [1 - Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) (1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}))] \quad (17b)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to Proposition 4 by setting $(X_{j+1} + V^D(T_{j+1})) \geq 0$.

3. Bilateral Defaultable Derivative Valuation and Bilateral CVA

The default indicator \hat{j} for party j ($j=A, B$) is a random variable with a Bernoulli distribution, which takes value 1 with default probability Q_j , and value 0 with survival probability S_j . Consider a pair of random variables (\hat{A}, \hat{B}) that has a bivariate Bernoulli distribution as summarized in Table 1.

Table 1. Bivariate Bernoulli Distribution

This table shows the joint and marginal distributions of a bivariate Bernoulli distribution of \hat{A} and \hat{B} . Marginally, each random variable \hat{j} ($\hat{j} = \hat{A}, \hat{B}$) follows a univariate Bernoulli distribution that takes value 1 with default probability Q_j and value 0 with survival probability S_j . $\gamma = \rho \sqrt{Q_A S_A Q_B S_B}$ where ρ is the correlation coefficient of \hat{A} and \hat{B} .

		Joint Distribution		Marginal Distribution
		$\hat{A}=1$	$\hat{A}=0$	
Joint Distribution	$\hat{B}=1$	$Q_B Q_A + \gamma$	$Q_B S_A - \gamma$	Q_B
	$\hat{B}=0$	$S_B Q_A - \gamma$	$S_B S_A + \gamma$	S_B
Marginal Distribution		Q_A	S_A	

3.1. Single Payment Cases

We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period.

Proposition 5: *The bilateral risky value of the single payment derivative is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{O(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (18a)$$

where

$$O(t, T) = \exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} o(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t\right) \quad (18b)$$

$$o(t+i\Delta t) = r(t+i\Delta t) + 1_{V(t+(i+1)\Delta t) \geq 0} p_B(t+i\Delta t) + 1_{V(t+(i+1)\Delta t) < 0} p_A(t+i\Delta t) \quad (18c)$$

$$\begin{aligned} p_B(t+i\Delta t) = & (1 - \varphi_B(t+i\Delta t))h_B(t+i\Delta t) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(t+i\Delta t))h_A(t+i\Delta t) \\ & - (1 - \varphi_B(t+i\Delta t) - \bar{\varphi}_B(t+i\Delta t) + \varphi_{AB}(t+i\Delta t)) \\ & \times \left[\rho \sqrt{h_A(t+i\Delta t)h_B(t+i\Delta t)(1-h_B(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t)(1-h_A(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t)} \right. \\ & \left. + h_B(t+i\Delta t)h_A(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t \right] \end{aligned} \quad (18d)$$

$$\begin{aligned} p_A(t+i\Delta t) = & (1 - \varphi_A(t+i\Delta t))h_A(t+i\Delta t) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(t+i\Delta t))h_B(t+i\Delta t) \\ & - (1 - \varphi_A(t+i\Delta t) - \bar{\varphi}_A(t+i\Delta t) + \varphi_{AB}(t+i\Delta t)) \\ & \times \left[\rho \sqrt{h_A(t+i\Delta t)h_B(t+i\Delta t)(1-h_B(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t)(1-h_A(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t)} \right. \\ & \left. + h_B(t+i\Delta t)h_A(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t \right] \end{aligned} \quad (18e)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

For any time interval $(u, u + \Delta t)$, the bilateral risk-adjusted short rate $o(u)$ has a switching-type dependence on the sign of future value $V^D(u + \Delta t)$. Similar to Proposition 1, the valuation process given by Proposition 5 builds on itself in a backward recursive fashion and requires a backward induction valuation.

Proposition 5 provides a general form for pricing a bilateral risky single payment derivative. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, i.e. $\rho = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$, we derive the following corollary.

Corollary 5.1: *If parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, the bilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{\bar{O}(t,T)X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (19a)$$

where

$$\bar{O}(t,T) = \exp\left[-\int_t^T \bar{o}(u)du\right] \quad (19b)$$

$$\bar{o}(u) = r(u) + 1_{V^D(u) \geq 0} \bar{p}_B(u) + 1_{V^D(u) < 0} \bar{p}_A(u) \quad (19c)$$

$$\bar{p}_B(u) = (1 - \varphi_B(u))h_B(u) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(u))h_A(u) \quad (19d)$$

$$\bar{p}_A(u) = (1 - \varphi_A(u))h_A(u) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(u))h_B(u) \quad (19e)$$

The proof of this corollary becomes straightforward according to Proposition 5 by setting $\rho = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$, taking the limit as Δt approaches zero, and having $h_B(u)h_A(u)\Delta t^2 \approx 0$ for very small Δt .

Corollary 5.1 is the same as equation (2.5') in Duffie and Huang (1996), but their derivation is heuristic rather than rigorous.

The corresponding bilateral CVA of the single payment derivative in this case can be expressed as

$$CVA^B(t) = V^F(t) - V^D(t) = E\{D(t,T)X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\} - E\{\bar{O}(t,T)X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (20)$$

If we assume that a default may occur only on the payment dates, the default options become either European options or Bermudan options.

Proposition 6: *The bilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E[Y(t,T)X_T|\mathcal{F}_t] \quad (21a)$$

where

$$Y(t,T) = D(t,T)\left(1_{X_T \geq 0} y_B(t,T) + 1_{X_T < 0} y_A(t,T)\right) \quad (21b)$$

$$y_B(t,T) = S_B(t,T)S_A(t,T) + \varphi_B(T)Q_B(t,T)S_A(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)S_B(t,T)Q_A(t,T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)Q_B(t,T)Q_A(t,T) + \gamma(t,T)(1 - \varphi_B(T) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (21c)$$

$$y_A(t,T) = S_B(t,T)S_A(t,T) + \varphi_A(T)Q_A(t,T)S_B(t,T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)S_A(t,T)Q_B(t,T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)Q_B(t,T)Q_A(t,T) + \gamma(t,T)(1 - \varphi_B(T) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T) + \varphi_{AB}(T)) \quad (21d)$$

$$\gamma(t,T) = \rho \sqrt{S_B(t,T)Q_B(t,T)S_A(t,T)Q_A(t,T)} \quad (21e)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

Proposition 6 has a general form that applies in a particular situation where we assume that parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, i.e. $\rho = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$.

Corollary 6.1: *If parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, the bilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = E\{\bar{Y}(t, T)X_T | \mathcal{F}_t\} \quad (22a)$$

where

$$\bar{Y}(t, T) = D(t, T) \left(1_{X_T \geq 0} \bar{y}_B(t, T) + 1_{X_T < 0} \bar{y}_A(t, T) \right) \quad (22b)$$

$$\bar{y}_B(t, T) = S_B(t, T)S_A(t, T) + \varphi_B(T)Q_B(t, T)S_A(t, T) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T)S_B(t, T)Q_A(t, T) \quad (22c)$$

$$\bar{y}_A(t, T) = S_B(t, T)S_A(t, T) + \varphi_A(T)Q_A(t, T)S_B(t, T) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T)S_A(t, T)Q_B(t, T) \quad (22d)$$

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to Proposition 6 by setting $\rho = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$.

3.2. Multiple Payments Cases

We divide any payment date period (T_{i-1}, T_i) into n_i very small time intervals (Δt) and assume that a default may occur only at the end of each very small period.

Proposition 7: *The bilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[(O(t, T_i))X_i | \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (23a)$$

where

$$O(t, T_i) = \exp \left[- \sum_{j=0}^{\sum_{k=1}^{n_i} n_k - 1} o(t + j\Delta t) \Delta t \right] \quad (23b)$$

$$o(t + j\Delta t) = r(t + j\Delta t) + 1_{V_{(t+(j+1)\Delta t)} \geq 0} p_B(t + j\Delta t) + 1_{V_{(t+(j+1)\Delta t)} < 0} p_A(t + j\Delta t) \quad (23c)$$

$$\begin{aligned}
p_B(t + j\Delta t) &= (1 - \varphi_B(t + j\Delta t))h_B(t + j\Delta t) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_B(t + j\Delta t))h_A(t + j\Delta t) \\
&\quad - (1 - \varphi_B(t + j\Delta t) - \bar{\varphi}_B(t + j\Delta t) + \varphi_{AB}(t + j\Delta t)) \\
&\quad \times \left[\rho \sqrt{h_A(t + j\Delta t)h_B(t + j\Delta t)(1 - h_B(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t)(1 - h_A(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + h_B(t + j\Delta t)h_A(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t \right] \tag{23d}
\end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
p_A(t + j\Delta t) &= (1 - \varphi_A(t + j\Delta t))h_A(t + j\Delta t) + (1 - \bar{\varphi}_A(t + j\Delta t))h_B(t + j\Delta t) \\
&\quad - (1 - \varphi_A(t + j\Delta t) - \bar{\varphi}_A(t + j\Delta t) + \varphi_{AB}(t + j\Delta t)) \\
&\quad \times \left[\rho \sqrt{h_A(t + j\Delta t)h_B(t + j\Delta t)(1 - h_B(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t)(1 - h_A(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t)} \right. \\
&\quad \left. + h_B(t + j\Delta t)h_A(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t \right] \tag{23e}
\end{aligned}$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

Proposition 7 provides a general form for pricing a bilateral multiple payment derivative. Applying it to a particular situation in which we assume that parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, i.e. $\rho = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$, we derive the following corollary.

Corollary 7.1: *If parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, the bilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the CTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\bar{O}(t, T_i)\right)X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \tag{24}$$

where $\bar{O}(t, T_i)$ is defined in (19).

The default options of a defaultable derivative under the CTM are American style options, while the default options under the DTM are Bermudan style ones.

Proposition 8: *The bilateral risky value of the multiple payments derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} Y(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t\right] \tag{25a}$$

where $t = T_0$ and

$$Y(T_j, T_{j+1}) = D(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left(1_{(X_{j+1} + V^D(T_{j+1})) \geq 0} y_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + 1_{(X_{j+1} + V^D(T_{j+1})) < 0} y_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) \tag{25b}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
y_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) &= S_B(T_j, T_{j+1})S_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \varphi_B(T_{j+1})Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})S_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1})S_B(T_j, T_{j+1})Q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) \\
&\quad + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})Q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \gamma(T_j, T_{j+1}) \left(1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1}) \right) \tag{25c}
\end{aligned}$$

$$y_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) = S_B(T_j, T_{j+1})S_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \varphi_A(T_{j+1})Q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})S_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \bar{\varphi}_A(T_{j+1})S_A(T_j, T_{j+1})Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})Q_A(T_j, T_{j+1}) + \gamma(T_j, T_{j+1})(1 - \varphi_B(T_{j+1}) - \bar{\varphi}_B(T_{j+1}) + \varphi_{AB}(T_{j+1})) \quad (25d)$$

$$\gamma(T_j, T_{j+1}) = \rho \sqrt{S_B(T_j, T_{j+1})Q_B(T_j, T_{j+1})S_A(T_j, T_{j+1})Q_A(T_j, T_{j+1})} \quad (25e)$$

Proof: See the Appendix.

Proposition 8 has a general form that applies in a particular situation where we assume that parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, i.e. $\rho = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$.

Corollary 8.1: *If parties A and B do not default simultaneously and have independent default risks, the bilateral risky value of the single payment derivative under the DTM is given by*

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E \left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} \bar{Y}(T_j, T_{j+1}) \right) X_i \mid \mathcal{F}_t \right] \quad (26)$$

where $\bar{Y}(T_j, T_{j+1})$ is defined in (22).

The proof of this corollary is easily obtained according to Proposition 8 by setting $\rho = 0$ and $\varphi_{AB} = 0$.

5. Numerical Results

In this section, we present some numerical results for risky valuations and CVA calculations based on the theory and the practical framework described above.

5.1. Comparison Between the CTM and the DTM

Here we use unilateral credit risk as an example. Assume that party B has an ‘A’ rating and a constant default recovery rate of 70%. Party A is default-free. All calculations are from the perspective of party A.

Then, we use a 10-year semi-annual fixed rate coupon bond to analog a multiple payments instrument. Assume that the principal is a unit and that the annual coupon rate of the fixed-rate coupon bond is 4%. The risk-free and risky values and the CVAs are calculated according to Corollary 3.2 and Corollary 4.1, shown in Table 4. The results confirm that the DTM and the CTM produce very close results.

Table 2. The Numerical Results of a 6-month Maturity Single Payment Derivative

This table shows the present risk-free and unilateral risky values, and the unilateral CVAs of a 6-month maturity single payment derivative calculated under both the CTM and the DTM. The derivative has only one payoff at 6-month maturity and a unit principal. Difference of CVA = $1 - \text{DTM-CVA} / \text{CTM-CVA}$.

Risk-Free Value	CTM		DTM		Difference of CVA
	Risky Value	CVA	Risky Value	CVA	
0.998168	0.997026	0.001142	0.997028	0.001140	0.1334%

Table 3. The Numerical Results of a 1-year Maturity Single Payment Derivative

This table shows the present risk-free and unilateral risky values, and the unilateral CVAs of a 1-year maturity single payment derivative computed under both the CTM and the DTM. The derivative has only one payoff at 1-year maturity and a unit principal. Difference of CVA = $1 - \text{DTM-CVA} / \text{CTM-CVA}$.

Risk-Free Value	CTM		DTM		Difference of CVA
	Risky Value	CVA	Risky Value	CVA	
0.995693	0.993422	0.002271	0.993428	0.002265	0.2658%

Table 4 The Numerical Results of a 10-Year Maturity Multiple Payments Derivative

This table shows the present risk-free and unilateral risky values, and the unilateral CVAs of a 10-year maturity multiple payments derivative calculated under both the CTM and the DTM. The derivative has a unit principal and semi-annual payments with an annual coupon rate of 4%. Difference of CVA = $1 - \text{DTM-CVA} / \text{CTM-CVA}$.

Risk-Free Value	CTM		DTM		Difference of CVA
	Risky Value	CVA	Risky Value	CVA	
1.122892	1.032344	0.090547	1.032901	0.089990	0.6153%

5.2. Impact of Margin Agreements

We use the CIR (Cox-Ingersoll-Ross) models for interest rate and hazard rate scenario generations, the modified GBM (Geometric Brownian Motion) models for equity and collateral evolutions, and the BK

(Black Karasinski) models for foreign exchange dynamics. Table 5 illustrates that if party A has an infinite collateral threshold $H_A = \infty$ i.e. no collateral requirement on A , the bilateral CVA value increases, while the threshold H_B increases. Table 6 shows that if party B has an infinite collateral threshold $H_B = \infty$, the bilateral CVA value actually decreases, while the threshold H_A increases. This reflects the bilateral impact of the collaterals on the bilateral CVA. The impact is mixed in Table 7 when both parties have finite collateral thresholds.

Table 5. The Impact of Collateral Threshold H_B on the Bilateral CVA

H_B denotes the collateral threshold of party B and H_A denotes the collateral threshold of party A . We set $H_A = \infty$ and change H_B only.

Collateral Threshold H_B	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
CVA	19,550.91	20,528.65	21,368.44	22,059.30

Table 6. The Impact of Collateral Threshold H_A on the Bilateral CVA

H_B denotes the collateral threshold of party B and H_A denotes the collateral threshold of party A . We set $H_B = \infty$ and change H_A only.

Collateral Threshold H_A	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
CVA	28,283.64	25,608.92	23,979.11	22,059.30

Table 7. The Impact of Both Collateral Thresholds on the Bilateral CVA

H_B denotes the collateral threshold of party B and H_A denotes the collateral threshold of party A . Both of them are changed.

Collateral Threshold H_B	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
Collateral Threshold H_A	10.1 Mil	15.1 Mil	20.1 Mil	Infinite (∞)
CVA	25,752.98	22,448.45	23,288.24	22,059.30

5.3. Impact of Wrong or Right Way Risk

We use an equity swap as an example. Assume the correlation between the underlying equity price and the credit quality (hazard rate) of party B is ρ . The impact of the correlation on the CVA is shown in Table 8. The results state that the CVA increases when the absolute value of the negative correlation increases.

Table 8. Impact of Wrong Way Risk on the Bilateral CVA

We use an equity swap as an example and assume that there is a negative correlation between the equity price and the credit quality of party B .

Correlation ρ	0	-50%	-100%
CVA	165.15	205.95	236.99

6. Conclusion

For completeness, our theoretical study covers various cases. We find that the valuation of defaultable derivatives and their CVAs, in most situations, has a backward recursive nature and requires a backward induction valuation. An intuitive explanation is that two counterparties implicitly sell each other an option to default when entering into a defaultable transaction. If we assume that a default may occur at any time, the default options are American style options. If we assume that a default may only happen on the payment dates, the default options are either European options or Bermudan options. Both Bermudan and American options require backward induction valuations.

Based on our theory, we propose a novel cash-flow-based practical framework for calculating the bilateral risky value and bilateral CVA at the counterparty portfolio level. This framework can easily incorporate various credit mitigation techniques, such as netting agreements and margin agreements, and can capture wrong/right way risk. Numerical results show that these credit mitigation techniques and wrong/right way risk have significant impacts on CVA.

Appendix

Proof of Proposition 1: Under the unilateral credit risk assumption, only the default risk of one party appears to be relevant, i.e., we only consider the default risk when the derivative is in the money. We divide the time period (t, T) into n very small intervals (Δt) and use the approximation $\exp(y) \approx 1 + y$ for very small y . Assume that a default may occur only at the end of each small period. The survival and the default probabilities for the period $(t, t + \Delta t)$ are given by

$$\widehat{S}_B(t) := S_B(t, t + \Delta t) = \exp(-h_B(t)\Delta t) \approx 1 - h_B(t)\Delta t \quad (\text{A1a})$$

$$\widehat{Q}_B(t) := Q_B(t, t + \Delta t) = 1 - \exp(-h_B(t)\Delta t) \approx h_B(t)\Delta t \quad (\text{A1b})$$

At time $t + \Delta t$ the derivative either defaults or survives. The risky value of the derivative at t is given by

$$\begin{aligned} V^D(t) &= E \left\{ \exp(-r(t)\Delta t) \left[1_{V^D(t+\Delta t) \geq 0} \left(\widehat{S}_B(t) + \varphi_B(t)\widehat{Q}_B(t) \right) + 1_{V^D(t+\Delta t) < 0} \right] V^D(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right\} \\ &\approx E \left\{ \exp(-r(t)\Delta t) \left[1_{V^D(t+\Delta t) \geq 0} \left(1 - h_B(t)\Delta t + \varphi_B(t)h_B(t)\Delta t \right) + 1_{V^D(t+\Delta t) < 0} \right] V^D(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right\} \\ &\approx E \left\{ \exp(-c_B(t)\Delta t) V^D(t + \Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_t \right\} \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A2a})$$

where 1_Y is an indicator function that is equal to one if Y is true and zero otherwise; and

$$1_{V^D(t+\Delta t) \geq 0} + 1_{V^D(t+\Delta t) < 0} = 1 \quad (\text{A2b})$$

$$c_B(t) = r(t) + 1_{V^D(t+\Delta t) \geq 0} h_B(t)(1 - \varphi_B(t)) \quad (\text{A2c})$$

Similarly, we have

$$V^D(t + \Delta t) = E \left\{ \exp(-c_B(t + \Delta t)\Delta t) V^D(t + 2\Delta t) \middle| \mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t} \right\} \quad (\text{A3})$$

Note that $\exp(-c_B(t)\Delta t)$ is $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable. By definition, an $\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}$ -measurable random variable is a random variable whose value is known at time $t + \Delta t$. Based on the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V^D(t) &= E\left\{\exp(-c_B(t)\Delta t)V^D(t+\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= E\left\{\exp(-c_B(t)\Delta t)E\left[\exp(-c_B(t+\Delta t)\Delta t)V^D(t+2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right]|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= E\left\{E\left[\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 c_B(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V^D(t+2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_{t+\Delta t}\right]|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= E\left\{\exp\left(-\sum_{i=0}^1 c_B(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t\right)V^D(t+2\Delta t)|\mathcal{F}_t\right\}
\end{aligned} \tag{A4}$$

By recursively deriving from t forward over T , where $V^D(T) = X_T$, the price can be expressed as

$$V^D(t) = E\left\{\exp\left[-\sum_{i=0}^{n-1} c_B(t+i\Delta t)\Delta t\right]X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left\{C_B(t,T)X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \tag{A5a}$$

where

$$c_B(t+i\Delta t) = r(t+i\Delta t) + 1_{V^D(t+(i+1)\Delta t) \geq 0} h_B(t+i\Delta t)(1 - \varphi_B(t+i\Delta t)) \tag{A5b}$$

Proof of Proposition 2: Under the unilateral credit risk assumption, we only consider the default risk when the derivative is in the money. Assume that a default may only occur on the payment date.

Therefore, the risky value of the derivative at t is given by

$$\begin{aligned}
V^D(t) &= E\left\{D(t,T)\left[1_{X_T \geq 0}(S_B(t,T) + \varphi_B(T)Q_B(t,T)) + 1_{X_T < 0}\right]X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= E\left\{D(t,T)\left[1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0}(1 - \varphi_B(T))Q_B(t,T)\right]X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} = E\left[G_B(t,T)X_T|\mathcal{F}_t\right]
\end{aligned} \tag{A6a}$$

where

$$1_{X_T \geq 0} + 1_{X_T < 0} = 1 \tag{A6b}$$

$$S_B(t,T) = 1 - Q_B(t,T) \tag{A6c}$$

$$G_B(t,T) = D(t,T)\left[1 - 1_{X_T \geq 0}Q_B(t,T)(1 - \varphi_B(T))\right] \tag{A6d}$$

Proof of Proposition 3: We divide any payment date period (T_{i-1}, T_i) into n_i very small time intervals (Δt) . On the first cash flow payment date T_1 , let $V^D(T_1)$ denote the value of the risky derivative excluding the current cash flow X_1 . Both $V^D(T_1)$ and X_1 could be positive or negative. According to Proposition 1, the risky value of the derivative at t is given by

$$V^D(t) = E\left[C_B(t,T_1)(X_1 + V^D(T_1))|\mathcal{F}_t\right] \tag{A7}$$

where $C_B(t,T_1)$ is defined in (A5)

Similarly, we have

$$V^D(T_1) = E\left[C_B(T_1, T_2)(X_2 + V^D(T_2))\middle|\mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right] \quad (\text{A8})$$

Note that $C_B(t, T_1)$ is \mathcal{F}_{T_1} -measurable. According to the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned} V^D(t) &= E\left[C_B(t, T_1)(X_1 + V^D(T_1))\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right] = E\left[C_B(t, T_1)X_1\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right] \\ &\quad + E\left\{C_B(t, T_1)\left[E\left(C_B(T_1, T_2)X_2\middle|\mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right) + E\left(C_B(T_1, T_2)V^D(T_2)\middle|\mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right)\right]\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\ &= \sum_{i=1}^2 E\left\{C_B(t, T_i)X_i\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right\} + E\left[C_B(t, T_2)V^D(T_2)\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right] \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A9a})$$

where

$$C_B(t, T_2) = C_B(t, T_1)C_B(T_1, T_2) = \exp\left[-\sum_{j=0}^{n_1+n_2-1} c_B(t + j\Delta t)\Delta t\right] \quad (\text{A9b})$$

By recursively deriving from T_2 forward over T_m , where $V^D(T_m) = X_m$, we have

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[(C_B(t, T_i))X_i\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (\text{A10})$$

Proof of Proposition 4: Let $t = T_0$. Assume that a default may only occur on the payment dates.

On the first payment date T_1 , let $V^D(T_1)$ denote the risky value of the derivative excluding the current cash flow X_1 . According to Proposition 2, the risky value of the derivative at t is given by

$$V^D(t) = E\left[G_B(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V^D(T_1))\middle|\mathcal{F}_t\right] \quad (\text{A11a})$$

where

$$G_B(T_0, T_1) = D(T_0, T) \left[1 - 1_{(X_1 + V^D(T_1)) \geq 0} Q_B(T_0, T_1)(1 - \varphi_B(T_1)) \right] \quad (\text{A11b})$$

Similarly, we have

$$V^D(T_1) = E\left[G_B(T_1, T_2)(X_2 + V^D(T_2))\middle|\mathcal{F}_{T_1}\right] \quad (\text{A12})$$

Note that $G_B(T_0, T_1)$ is \mathcal{F}_{T_1} -measurable. According to the *taking out what is known* and *tower* properties of conditional expectation, we have

$$\begin{aligned}
V^D(t) &= E[G_B(T_0, T_1)(X_1 + V^D(T_1)) | \mathcal{F}_t] = E[G_B(T_0, T_1)X_1 | \mathcal{F}_t] \\
&\quad + E\left\{G_B(T_0, T_1)\left[E(G_B(T_1, T_2)X_2 | \mathcal{F}_{T_1}) + E(G_B(T_1, T_2)V^D(T_2) | \mathcal{F}_{T_1})\right] | \mathcal{F}_t\right\} \\
&= \sum_{i=1}^2 E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} G_B(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] + E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^1 G_B(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)V^D(T_2) | \mathcal{F}_t\right]
\end{aligned} \tag{A13}$$

By recursively deriving from T_2 forward over T_m , where $V^D(T_m) = X_m$, we have

$$V^D(t) = \sum_{i=1}^m E\left[\left(\prod_{j=0}^{i-1} G_B(T_j, T_{j+1})\right)X_i | \mathcal{F}_t\right] \tag{A14}$$

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